

Effect of Composition on the Huggins Constant, k' for Methyl Methacrylate-Acrylonitrile Copolymers*

A. K. KASHYAP, C. RAMI REDDY and (MRS.) V. KALPAGAM*

Department of Inorganic and Physical Chemistry, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore 560012

Manuscript received 13 September 1975; revised 2 December 1975; accepted 6 December 1975

The variation of the Huggins constant (k') with composition for Methylmethacrylate-Acrylonitrile copolymer in three different solvents, 2-butanone, acetonitrile and N,N'-dimethylformamide is described in this paper. This variation is noticed to be both composition and solvent dependent.

THE Huggins constant k' is independent of molecular weight for polymer fractions of similar polydispersity and structure¹. The variation of Huggins constant with various parameters such as solvent, molecular weight, temperature and structure has been studied for a number of homopolymer systems, but the study of the influence of composition on k' for copolymers is of recent origin^{2,3,4}. The present work describes the variation of k' with composition for the methylmethacrylate-acrylonitrile (MMA-AN) copolymers in three different solvents—2-butanone (MEK), acetonitrile (MeCN) and N,N' dimethylformamide (DMF).

Experimental

MMA-AN copolymers of 4 different compositions prepared by free radical initiation with benzoylperoxide as the initiator were used for this study. Percentage of conversion and other details are given elsewhere⁵.

Viscosity measurements were carried out in the solvents—DMF, MEK and MeCN at 30°. Solvent purification was carried out by the standard procedure⁶. Solvents were distilled just prior to use. Ubbelohde suspended level viscometers which were constructed in this laboratory were used for the determination of intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ and k' .

Results and Discussion

k' and $[\eta]$ values are tabulated along with the composition of the copolymers in Table 1.

From the Table, it is seen that polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) shows an increase in k' from the normal value of about 0.40 in the good solvents like MEK and DMF, to a value 1.21 in the θ -solvent acetonitrile⁷. Such type of behaviour has also been noticed for butyl and 2-ethylbutyl methacrylate polymers^{8,9}. This can be explained in terms of association of the polymer in the solvent.

The k' value in MEK decreases initially upto about 0.3 mole fraction of AN and then increases upto 0.50 indicating that the solvent becomes poorer as the AN unit is increased further in the copolymer chain. This is further supported by the fact that the fourth copolymer MA4 is not soluble in MEK.

The k' value in MeCN decreases as the composition of the copolymer is varied from 0.289 mole fraction of AN to 0.415 mole fraction of AN, but increases further as the AN content is increased in the copolymer. A minimum in the value of k' at 0.5 mole fraction of AN is observed. Such a behaviour in k' has also been noticed for St-AN and St-MA copolymer systems^{2,3}.

The k' value in DMF shows very little decrease on the increase of AN content from 0.289 m.f. to 0.415 m.f. of AN. A further increase in AN content shows a sharp decrease in k' value. As the k' value of PAN is known to be 0.33,¹⁰ the curve is extended to 1.0 m.f. of AN, which gives a minimum at 0.65 m.f. of AN.

TABLE I—HUGGINS CONSTANT AND INTRINSIC VISCOSITY VALUES FOR THE COPOLYMERS AT 30°

Polymer	Mole fraction of AN in copolymer	k'			$[\eta]$		
		MEK	MeCN	DMF	MEK	MeCN	DMF
PMMA	0.001	0.39	1.21	0.40	0.357	0.166	0.656
MA1	0.289	0.25	0.37	0.36	0.733	0.635	0.883
MA2	0.415	0.38	0.33	0.35	0.613	0.660	0.980
MA3	0.566	0.50	0.35	0.17	0.460	0.612	0.947
MA4	0.657	—	0.36	0.13	—	0.564	0.827
PAN	1.000	—	—	0.33	—	—	—

* This paper was presented at the Annual Convention of Chemistry, 1975 at Roorkee University, Roorkee.

Fig. 1

From the above observations, it can be said that the value of k' is affected with the composition of a binary copolymer and this change is not a uniform one.

Depending on the solvent power, a change in the k' value is observed. Though it is difficult to presume the solvent power in these systems, without the knowledge of exponent 'a' (in the Mark-Houwink equation) and other parameters such as long-range interaction parameters, the solvent power of the above three solvents may be broadly classified as $DMF > MeCN > MEK$, which is not the same for all the copolymers. As the composition of the copolymers changes, the solvent power is observed to change in the following way :

- MA1 : $MEK > DMF > MeCN$
 MA2 : $MeCN > DMF > MEK$
 MA3 : $DMF > MeCN > MEK$
 MA4 : $DMF > MeCN$

In case of random azeotropic copolymers, k' is found to be lower than the parent homopolymers¹¹. This is found to be true for block copolymers also⁴, where the value of k' reaches a minimum at about 0.5 m.f.⁴

For copolymers other than the above two types, the decrease of k' value is not a uniform one. There are cases in literature when the minimum of k' value with change of composition is at about 0.5 m.f.^{2,3,4} But in the present system, the decrease of k' is of random nature. This study clearly shows that the variation of k' with composition is also strongly solvent dependent. The minima in case of MeCN is at about 0.5 m.f. in accordance with the other workers^{2,3,4}. In case of the other two solvents, the variation of k' is different. In case of MEK, the minimum is at about 0.3 m.f. of AN and the system is insoluble when the composition is above 0.566 mole fraction of AN. In case of DMF, when the AN content is increased in MMA backbone, the variation in the k' is very small till about a composition of 0.415 mole fraction of AN. With further increase in AN content, the change in the k' value is pronounced and the minima is observed at 0.65 m.f. of AN.

Hence, from this study it can be concluded that the value of k' is dependent strongly both on the composition of the copolymer as well as the nature of the solvent.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.K.K) is grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (New Delhi) for the award of a junior research fellowship.

References

1. M. L. HUGGINS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2716.
2. YUKO SHIMURA, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1966, 4 (A-2), 423.
3. H. FISCHER and W. MACHTLE, *Kolloid-Zeitschrift und Zeitschrift für Polymers*, 1969, 230, 221.
4. G. M. BARNETT, P. MEARES and C. PATON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1962, 58, 737.
5. A. K. KASHYAP, C. RAMI REDDY and MRS. V. KALPAGAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).
6. A. WEISSBERGER and E. S. PHOSKAUER, "Organic Solvents, Physical properties and methods of purification", 3rd Edition Interscience Publishers, New York 1970.
7. G. E. COHN, GINS BERG, T. G. FOX and H. F. MASON, *Polymer*, 1962, 3, 97.
8. S. N. CHINAI and R. A. GUZZI, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1956, 21, 417.
9. F. E. DIDOT, S. N. CHINAI and D. W. LEVI, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1960, 43, 557.
10. R. L. CLELAND and W. H. STOCKMAYER, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1955, 17, 473.
11. S. N. CHINAI, J. D. MATLAK, A. L. RESNICK and R. S. SAMUEL, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1955, 17, 391.